

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF CREATING POSITIVE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT: Teaching students and young children is not an easy matter. So, all educators should be very careful to give knowledge to the young generation. The purpose of this article is to search for effective ways of creating positive classroom management. Moreover, it discusses classroom management in foreign language lessons.

KEY WORDS: classroom management, teaching, effective teaching methods.

Educators have varied types of roles in a specific classroom, however the most significant one is classroom management. Effective teaching and progressive learning can not be replaced with impoverished managed classroom. From preparing for the year of school to dealing with bullying to forging relationship with administrator have been covered by the method of successful classroom management. As for new teachers, they frequently buy into the myth that the ability to manage a classroom is an inherent feature. Managing class is considered to be the establishment of organizing the whole class which begins with interaction between teacher and learners and ends with the behaviour of students. Educating other language to ESL students is likely to have burdens, teachers are facing during teaching process.

According to the help of hi-tech technologies, we have accepted new methods of teaching foreign language and refused already antediluvian ideas about grammar or text-translation methods. Organizing a lesson began to be more entertaining, full of games with using visual aids, audios and digital tools which help to improve students' learning skills and create positive environment in the classroom. Classroom management refers to all those essential activities which are highly necessary not only to create but also to maintain a supportive and orderly atmosphere. It includes planning and preparation of teaching and learning materials, organisation of the materials, decoration of the classroom, creation of expectation and establishment and enforcement of rules in the classroom (Tan, Parsons, Hinson and Sardo-Brown, 2003).

Effective teaching methods are considered to include affects of teaching quality and learning. In the classroom, where teachers are respected, children are safe, effective teachers must be able to create a sound, supportive and

friendly to their students. For this purpose, condition of cooperation , discipline and responsibility both for teachers and student should be invented by these types of educators.

The usage of these kinds of features aid teachers to soak the whole class up in the learning process. Nowadays , we can not see any student , which are interested in spelling tasks, learning new words , but they are more visual-oriented and kinaesthetic learners. Taking everything into consideration teacher should prepare for his or her students activities and strategies which include all learners to participate in the process of the lesson. Most students are given engaging, motivating and challenging learning experiences by foreign language teachers. However, there are lots of essential problems in terms of teaching foreign language , for instance , over-crowded classrooms, poor literature problems, the lack of information and other circumstances.

Harmer(1991) lists different roles of teacher in a language classroom. They are: educator as a assessor, controller, organizer, prompter, participant , resource, provider , investigator and tutor. Similarly, Ghimire(2010) supported Hedge by listing the following role of teachers.

Canter(2001) argues that “ There are two goals of classroom management. First , to create annd maintain a highly supportive learning environment and second , to promote a safe classroom community so that students` interest, motivation and involvement in the learning process are maintained”. All of the teachers should follow these rules , moreover , they must more than people expected . Being a teacher is one of the most important and glorious jobs in the world . So that, they need to prove theirselves and try to be good at every single aspects of life.

There is no any difficult thing to do , only teachers must have different kinds of activities which interest pupil to learn more this language , if they do not it is straight forward to students to be actively involved. Effective classroom management have significant effects for the climate, motivation, discipline, respect and academic performaanace of students in education system.

In conclusion, in order to solve burdens in classroom, educators must be able to create conducive learning environment where students are likely to find care, respect, opportunity for both personal and social growth. For this purpose, teachers and student should follow the established regulations and procedures as possible as they can.

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